

Spatial pattern of COVID-19 mortality and its relationship with socioeconomic and environmental factors in England

Zhiqiang Feng

School of Geosciences, University of Edinburgh

26 March 2021

Summary

This paper investigated the spatial pattern of COVID-19 mortality and the socioeconomic and environmental determinants. The COVID-19 mortality data was acquired from the Office for National Statistics including all deaths from March to July, 2020 in England. SaTScan and GWR were separately used in the analysis of hotspots and the association of COVID-19 mortality rates with socioeconomic and environmental factors. The results show that there were significant spatial inequalities of COVID-19 mortality and age, ethnicity, deprivation and pollution were all related to COVID-19 mortality.

KEYWORDS: COVID-19 mortality, hotspot, SaTScan, GWR, England

1. Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic has claimed over two million lives worldwide and also resulted in serious socio and economic consequences. So far epidemiological studies have improved our knowledge on the aetiology of COVID-19-related disease. However, there is still considerable unknown on factors contributing to disease severity. In this paper we explore the spatial pattern of COVID-19 mortality and its association with socioeconomic and environmental factors in England. We used SaTScan to explore the hotspots of COVID-19 mortality and geographically weighted regression (GWR) to examine the association between mortality and socioeconomic and environmental determinants.

2. Data

The COVID-19 death data is acquired from ONS (Office for National Statistics). Data include all deaths of three months from 1st of March to the 31st of July, 2020 when the first wave of COVID-19 pandemic in England occurred. The data were the counts of deaths by month in Middle Lower Super Output Areas (MSOA, average population was 8200) in England.

The age composition and population density data was from the ONS mid-year population estimates in 2018. The ethnicity and care home data were from the 2011 census. Income deprivation data was percentage of people in low income and was obtained from the index of multiple deprivation (IMD) statistics of 2019 (MHCLG, 2019).

In order to adjust for viral exposure we include measures including population density, and the level of viral transmission by days since the first day when there were 10 confirmed COVID-19 case in the local authority. Population density was computed using the mid-year population estimates in 2019 in persons per hectare. The Public Health England (PHE) data was used to calculate the number of days since the day when 10 laboratory confirmed cases in a local authority were identified.

The data of PM_{2.5} was obtained from DEFRA (Department for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs) modelled annual average pollutant concentrations at a 1km by 1km resolution from 2014 to 2018. The five year average of four pollutant concentrations were used to indicate long term exposure to air pollution. Concentration values for each of the pollutants were for 1km grid-squares (<https://ukair.defra.gov.uk/data/pcm-data>), which was interpolated to MSOA level using the point-in-polygon method.

3. Methods

We identified hotspots of COVID-19 mortality using the SaTScan program (Kulldorff and Information Management Services, Inc. 2018). The program was implemented to scan for areas with high rates of COVID-19 deaths. The analyses were carried out using the Poisson probability model, 999 Monte Carlo replications to test for significance. The number of COVID-19 deaths by MSOA was used as the case file, the population from the 2019 was used as the population file, and the easting and northing of the centroids of each MSOA were used in the coordinates file. The maximum spatial cluster size was set to 3% of the population at risk in order to avoid large clusters.

We estimated the relationship between COVID-19 deaths and socioeconomic and environmental factors using an ordinary least square and GWR (Brunson et al 1996). The COVID-19 death rate (deaths per million) was the outcome variable. The independent variables were standardised before entering into the model. All mappings were done in ArcMap v 10.6.1 (ESRI Inc., 2018). Statistical analysis was carried out using the GWR 4.0 package (Nakaya, 2009).

4. Results

The total number of COVID-19 deaths were 49,232 in the five months from March to July with an average of 7 deaths across MSOAs. The total number of MSOAs included in our main analysis is 6,971, of which 195 had not reported any COVID-19 deaths by the end of July, 2020. The high death rates occurred mostly in London, Liverpool, Sunderland, Sheffield, Birmingham, and Cumbria. The average COVID-19 death rate in England varied markedly from March to July. The rate started from 81.1 per million in March and peaked at 525 per million in April, and then declined from 206 per million in May, 58 per million in June to 17 per million in July, 2020.

The COVID-19 mortality rates and hotspots of COVID-19 mortality for each month were presented in Figure 1. In March, the first month that the pandemic outbreak occurred in England 7 hotspots were identified, with five of them being in London and south east England. One hotspot was in Birmingham and one in Salford. In the April the hotspot spread to all over the country and the total number of hotspots increased to 26 with Liverpool, Newcastle being hotspots of higher risk of COVID-19 deaths. One notable large hotspot in Gloucestershire was highly likely to relate to the Cheltenham festival in March. It appears that there was divide between east and west of England with majority of hotspots being in west part of England. In May, the number of hotspots reduced slightly to 19. The biggest changes were the hotspots in London and Southeast London disappeared with one exception in the Dover area while a few more hotspots appeared in the Northampton, South Norfolk, and Penland. The hotspots in Northwest England largely remained. In June, the number of hotspots continued to decline. There was concentration of hotspots in northwest England and north Yorkshire. The hotspot in the Newcastle area disappeared. In contrast, the hotspot in the Dover area remained. In July only 6 hotspots existed. With a sharp decline in the number of infections and the number of death the hotspots scattered in southeast, east, northwest and midlands.

Figure 1 COVID-19 deaths (March to July, 2020) per million in middle super output areas, and hotspots in England

Table 1 Summary statistics of variables

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev	Min	Max
Death rate (per million)	889.6	667.7	0	6828.4
% Age 65 and over	13.68	4.99	0.44	37.06
% Black	3.26	6.32	0.00	54.50
% South Asian	5.12	10.34	0.00	81.14
% In care home	0.68	0.75	0.00	8.05
% Low income	0.13	0.08	0.01	0.49
Days from 10 confirmed cases in local authority	74.35	5.29	48	88
Population density (Persons/ha)	35.3	38.1	0.05	283.3
PM _{2.5} (µg/m ³)	9.75	2.10	5.04	14.60

Data sources: ONS, PHE, MHCLG.

The descriptive summary is presented in Table 1. The death rate was calculated based on accumulated deaths in five months from March to July. The average death rate was 889.6 per million with the maximum of 6828.4 per million. The OLS results are shown in Table 2.

The OLS model showed that as expected areas with a higher proportion of people aged over 65, higher proportion of Black and South Asian, higher proportion of people in care home, higher level of low

income people were all associated with higher risks of COVID-19 deaths. Areas where there was a longer duration in coronavirus infection was not linked to a higher risk of COVID-19 deaths. Population density was a significant predictor of COVID-19 death but the association was negative meaning the overall death rate was lower in higher densely populated areas. The air pollution indicator PM2.5 is associated with increased risks of COVID-19 death.

Table 2 Estimated coefficients from linear regression analysis

Variable	Estimate	Standard Error	T
Intercept	889.63	7.49	118.64
% 65 and over	98.50	11.34	8.68
% Low income	81.95	9.16	8.93
% Care home	218.84	7.92	27.62
Days since 10 confirmed cases in local authority	10.63	8.27	1.28
% Black	65.10	10.23	6.36
% South Asian	63.37	8.48	7.46
Persons per ha	-27.34	11.19	-2.44
PM2.5	44.35	11.04	4.01

Data sources: ONS, PHE, MHCLG.

Figure 2 Estimated coefficients from the GWR model

GWR analysis showed that the relationship between environmental factors and COVID-19 deaths vary greatly over space (Figure 2). For example although the global model showed the relationship between population density and COVID-19 mortality was negative but there were areas where the relationship was positive. The most consistent relationship is between the percentage of people in care home with a positive association across the whole England.

5. Conclusions

This paper demonstrated that the spatial pattern of COVID-19 mortality changed over the period of the first wave of the pandemic in England with the hotspots spreading in the peak months. The statistical models showed a number of socioeconomic and environmental variables are associated with the COVID-19 mortality and the relationship varied over geographical areas. It reveals that COVID-19 mortality displayed a significant spatial pattern that was related to age, ethnic composition and also areal pollution. The care home was the most important variable with the largest effect size which provides further evidence in terms of protecting vulnerable elderly in future pandemic. In future we may consider adding other variables like occupation structure and overcrowding so as to improve the model.

Acknowledgements

Thanks are due to the reviewer for their constructive comments.

References

- ESRI, Inc. Esri support ArcMap 10.6 (10.6.1) [Internet]. 2018 Available from: <https://support.esri.com/en/products/desktop/arcgis-desktop/arcmap/10-6-1> .
- Han, Y., Yang, L., Jia, K., Li, J., Feng, S., Chen, W., Zhao, W. and Pereira, P., 2021. Spatial distribution characteristics of the COVID-19 pandemic in Beijing and its relationship with environmental factors. *Science of the Total Environment*, 761, p.144257.
- Kim, S. and Castro, M.C., 2020. Spatiotemporal pattern of COVID-19 and government response in South Korea (as of May 31, 2020). *International Journal of Infectious Diseases*, 98, pp.328-333.
- Kulldorff and Information Management Services, Inc. 2018 SaTScan version 9.6: software for the spatial, temporal, and space-time scan statistics [Internet]. Available from: <https://www.satscan.org/> [cited 01.06.20].
- MHCLG (Ministry of Housing, Communities & Local Government). English indices of deprivation 2019: research report. GOV.UK. 2019. <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/english-indices-of-deprivation-2019-research-report> (accessed April 23, 2020).
- Nakaya, T. GWR 4.0. Available online: https://geodacenter.asu.edu/gwr_software (accessed on 26 December 2014).

Biographies

Zhiqiang Feng is a Senior Lecturer in quantitative human geography in the School of Geosciences, University of Edinburgh. His interests are in GIS, spatial analysis, longitudinal analysis and health geography.